

**THE IMPACT OF STRENGTH TRAINING ACTIVITIES ON THE
ENHANCEMENT OF SPEED IN SWIMMING FREESTYLE EVENTS**

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Abstract:

The current study aims to determine the impact of strength training on the growth of swimming speed in freestyle. Twenty male swimmers, aged 21 ± 2 , from Physical Education and sport sciences department, the Islamic university in Najaf, Iraq, make up the sample for this study. Ten of them are in the experimental group and ten are in the control group. The experimental group received strength training on alternate days, or three sessions per week, including biceps curls, bench presses, front presses, back presses, and so on, while the control group received general training for eight weeks. 50-meter freestyle swimming was done for the pre- and post-tests in order to gauge speed. The dependent t-test was used to examine the impacts of strength training exercises for the development of speed among free style event swimmers. It was discovered that there was a significant difference in the speed of free style event swimmers at the 0.05 level of significance. This study demonstrates that the experimental group's 50-meter freestyle swimming performance has improved as a result of strength training when compared to the controlling group. To achieve at an elite level in swimming, strength training is crucial. In order to maximize the benefits of land-based training, we should choose exercises that are mechanically relevant to swimming, especially those that require the swimmer to push themselves through the water, like the arm pull and leg kick.

Key Words: Strength Exercise, Free Style Swimming, Skeletal Muscle Growth

1. Introduction:

Strengthening is a form of physical activity that focuses on using resistance to cause muscular contraction, increasing skeletal muscle growth, strength, and anaerobic endurance. Swimming tactics, which are governed by competition regulations, are the ways in which swimmers move cyclically (MR et al. 2011, M et al. 2009).

Similar to other cycle sports like cycling and running, swimming success has been closely associated with physiological, technical, and physical capabilities. However, because moving across water requires more energy per unit of distance than moving on land, controlling the technical level may be crucial for boosting propulsion and lowering active drag (Shortwell et al. 2011, TM et al. 2011).

Because swimming is a physically demanding activity that calls for both strength and endurance, your focus while lifting weights should be on building strong muscles with great endurance. A minimal amount of fundamental endurance training, primarily in the form of stroke exercises, kicking, and pulling, is recommended for 50-meter sprinters. Instead of swimming at their anaerobic thresholds, the sprinters should aim for low to moderate swim speeds that resemble their aerobic thresholds. Their recovery time will be shortened with basic endurance training without compromising their sprint pace. It is not necessary for swimmers who focus on 50 races to perform threshold or overload endurance training. They don't need to increase the fast twitch muscle fibres' aerobic potential, and they definitely don't want to run the danger of having those fibres lose strength and contractile speed (Maglischo, 2003).

There are four recognised primary styles in competition swimming. With a few modest advancements over the past 30 to 40 years, they have remained mostly steady. The four primary swimming strokes are:

- Freestyle (Free)
- Breaststroke (Breast)
- Backstroke (Back)
- Butterfly (Fly)

The International Swimming Federation (FINA) defines freestyle as a swimming competition category where swimmers are only subject to very few limitations on their stroke. Since front crawls are often the quickest, they are virtually always employed in freestyle events.

2. The Study's Objectives:

- The study's findings will be used to critically examine how strength training exercises affect swimmers' ability to develop their free style swimming speed.
- Learning how important physical conditioning is for racket games would be beneficial.

- The study's findings will be useful in developing racket game players' physical conditioning regimens.
- It could also increase understanding of racket sports fitness.
- Players may use this study to examine their own physical fitness levels in relation to other racket games.

3. Methodology:

The study involved the selection of 20 participants in tennis, badminton, squash, and table tennis. The participants were 21 ± 2 years old, and the selection process was based on the purposive sample approach. The experimental group received strength training on alternate days, or three sessions per week, including biceps curls, bench presses, front presses, back presses, and so on, while the control group received general training for eight weeks.

4. Discussion and Conclusion:

This study demonstrates that the experimental group's 50-meter freestyle swimming performance has improved as a result of strength training when compared to the controlling group. In the 50-meter freestyle swimming pre-test, the experimental group's mean performance was 40.22; nevertheless, this performance improved to 37.20. The strength training in the meantime has helped the Means Experimental group improve by 3.02. In the 50-meter freestyle swimming pre-test, the control group's mean performance was 40.22; nevertheless, it dropped to 41.70. The overall training has resulted in a 1.48 drop in the Means Experimental group.

To achieve at an elite level in swimming, strength training is crucial. We must choose exercises with mechanical relevance to swimming action if we want to get the most out of land-based training. This is especially important for motions like the arm pull and leg kick, which help the swimmer move through the water. It is determined that the 50-meter freestyle swimming has improved as a result of strength training.

5. Variables - Speed:

Criteria measures: 50-meter freestyle swimming was done before and after the test to gauge speed. Analytical Statistics using the dependent t-test (paired t-test), the impact of strength training exercises on the development of speed in swimming free style events was determined. The significance threshold was established at 0.05 levels in order to evaluate the hypothesis.

6. Results:

Table 1: Presenting the 50-meter freestyle swimming performance of the swimming experimental group and the swimming-controlled group

50 M Free Style Swimming	N	Pre test	Post test	T	Sig
Experimental	10	40.22	37.20	-3.35	0.004
Control	10	40.22	41.70		

In 50 meters of freestyle swimming, (Table No. 1) displays the results of the Swimming Experimental Group and the Swimming Controlled Group. The experimental group's performance has improved while the controlled group's performance has declined.

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